

YAQUB ABU YUSUF FOUNDER OF STATE TAX THEORY**Rakhmanov Abdukakhor Absattorvich***TMA Termiz branch,**Youth issues and spiritual-educational**Deputy Director of Affairs,**Independent researcher**rahmonov_a.a@mail.ru*

Abstract. In this article, Yaqub Abu Yusuf, one of the greatest scholars in the Islamic world, made a great contribution to the development of science and culture through his socio-philosophical views, based on the analysis of a large number of taxes in practice in the caliphate, the book "Kitab ul-Kharaj" written about the Islamic tax system, the country's economic its role in life has been studied.

We formed new knowledge based on extensive and thorough study of Yaqub Abu Yusuf's personality and his work "Kitab ul-Kharaj", in particular his great efforts in the direction of national peace, material and spiritual life of citizens. Especially Abu Yusuf's development of the tax system, the description of tax types based on one by one accurate calculations, greatly helped the Islamic countries in the subsequent management system. We can see Islamic tax system in practice in some modern Islamic countries as well.

Keywords. Abu Yusuf, "Kitab ul-Kharaj", Islamic tax system, Arab caliphate, Islamic philosophical teachings.

Yaqub Abu Yusuf ibn Ibrahim al-Ansari al-Kufi, the disciple and follower of Abu Hanifa, the founder of the Hanafi order, known as Abu Yusuf in the Islamic world, died in 113 (A.H.735) was born in Kufa¹. He was a great scholar of

¹Abu Yusuf Yakub b. Ibrahim al-Kufi. Kitab al-Kharadj (Musulmanskoje nalogooblojenje) / Per. s arabskogo i komentarii A. E. Schmidt. Suprakomentarii k perevodu A. S. Bogolyubova. Podgotovka k izdaniyu, vstupit.statya i indicator A. A. Hismatulini. - St. Petersburg. 2001. – S.12.

jurisprudence and statesman. Abu Yusu was Abu Hanifa's best student and follower. After the death of Abu Hanifa, he continued his work and made a significant contribution to the spread of Hanafiism. Abbasid caliphs served in high positions during the Mahdi, Hadi and Rashid periods. They all adored him. He was promoted to the position of qazil-quzzat (chief judge) during the reign of Caliph Harun al-Rashid.

The work "Kitab ul-kharaj" also belongs to the category of works aimed at solving such issues. Its importance lies in the fact that, firstly, it greatly helped the Abbasid Empire in the systematized regulation of land taxes, which is the main source of state income in the country, and secondly, it established the social activities of the state in the financial sphere based on the methods and rules of the Hanafi sect and created conditions for its implementation.

The work "Kitab ul-Kharaj" is one of the ancient sources that have reached us, and the socio-economic relations of the first caliphate are illuminated. Abu Yusuf's work did not only focus on tax collection, but also focused on larger social issues. It is important that the author did not rely on a dry theory to explain it, but proved it with concrete factual materials.

"Kitab ul-Kharaj" was written by Abu Yusuf during the time of Chief Qazi on the order of Caliph Harun al-Rashid. The book is composed in the form of answers to the questions posed by the caliph. In this unique style, the questions on behalf of the caliph were formulated by the author himself. The original purpose of writing "Kitab ul-Kharaj" was to find an optimal balance between state revenues and expenses in practice. Abu Yusuf wrote his works in the interpretation of considering the obligations of the ruler to his subjects. It can be said that many works on this topic could be found in Muslim countries. On the issues of taxation in the early periods of Islam 21 books are known. But only three have reached our days.

About 550 hadiths are listed in "Kitab ul-Kharaj". However, Abu Yusuf did not only quote verses of the Holy Qur'an and hadiths, but used them as proofs in making jurisprudential rulings.

In this way, Abu Yusuf in his work "Kitab ul-Kharaj" explained the order of tax collection, its form, types of tax collection, how Muslims and non-Muslims should be treated, how the king's management should be carried out in state administration, and many other important issues.

Abu Yusuf wrote such works as "Kitab ul-asar", "Ar-raddu 'alaa Siyar ul-Awza'i" (refutation of Avza'i's book "as-Siyar"), "Conflict between Abu Hanifa and Ibn Abu Laila".

It is clear from his views that he was well aware of various aspects of tax administration. Before dealing with tax issues systematically, he emphasizes the need for "paying capacity of the tax payer", "reliability of tax collectors", efficient and honest tax administration². He emphasizes the need for the development of socio-economic infrastructure for the country's progress, and he also suggests how the state can cover such costs for building bridges and digging canals. For this, he emphasizes the need to introduce a fair and efficient tax system.

He pointed out that the main income of the state depends on taxes from cultivated land, so the new tax system will encourage more areas to be cultivated. He presented a series of proposals to the ruler to meet the needs of his people and make them live well in all aspects. He also emphasized the need for justice and equality in taxation. According to him, the ruler must keep public money in a safe manner and be responsible for its spending.

The main contribution of Abu Yusuf's views is in the field of public finance. His book also contains some considerations about markets and prices, such as how prices are determined and how different types of taxes affect them.

Abu Yusuf's views on the economic activities and obligations of the state are not found in other sources. We can find it only among his writings. First of all, before describing in detail the views on the sources of income for the state, expenditures, management policy, it is appropriate to study his views on the role of the state in

² Sabahiddin Azmi. Abu Yusuf's contribution to the theory of public finance. Dissertation submitted of the degree of master of philosophy in economics. India. 1995. - P.34.

economic life. In his treatise, Abu Yusuf elaborated on the main goals and tasks of the state. He said that the ruler is obliged to do things that protect the interests of his people.

Also, the ruler is responsible for supplying them with products necessary for the needs of the population and implementing the necessary supplies for the development of the economy. In his work, the goals of the state are reflected as follows:

1. Provision of the basic needs of the population.
2. To protect the religion and ensure the supremacy of the word of God.
3. Establish an honest and fair management system.
4. Comprehensive development of the economy.
5. Ensuring the general well-being of the people.³

In Abu Yusuf's view, it is important not only to spread Islam among the people, but also to practice it. In the books he wrote, he lays down the laws that people should follow. As a result, it is defined as the law of the state, not something that ordinary people follow in their daily lives. Of course, these services of his led to a lot of order in the society.

Abu Yusuf introduced a new method of khiroj tax in his work "Kitab ul-kharaj". In the period before Abu Yusuf, taxation of conquered lands was carried out according to the procedure introduced by Umar (RA). Abu Yusuf Umar (r.a.) deviated from the ruling and in his treatise proposed a method of taxation based on the distribution of the cultivated crop rather than on the size of the land - Muqasama.⁴ Analyzing the above points, we can come to the following conclusions: each of the works written by Abu Yusuf focused on some aspect of society and played an important role in its development. In particular, his work "Kitab ul-Kharaj" is considered a great work for Islamic jurisprudence in its time. Because he molded

³ Sabahiddin Azmi. Abu Yusuf's contribution to the theory of public finance. Dissertation submitted of the degree of master of philosophy in economics. India. 1995. - P.36.

⁴ Muqasama is a distribution system based on the quantity of crops grown by farmers.

the tax system with new theories and compiled it in a book. This book later served as the basis for legislation in many Islamic states.

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